

Chemical equilibrium studies on some bivalent metal chelates of cephalixin

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The stability constants of metal chelates of cephalixin (an antibiotic drug) with Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} , Zn^{II} ions have been evaluated pH-metrically in aqueous solutions at 25 and 30° and 0.1 M (NaClO_4) ionic strength. The ternary formation constants of metal chelates MLA, where M = bivalent ions, L = cephalixin and A = α -alanine, have also been determined potentiometrically; cephalixin behaves as primary ligand in presence of α -alanine as the secondary ligand. Stability constants are discussed in terms of the basicity of ligand, statistical and stereochemical phenomenon. Thermodynamic parameters have also been evaluated and discussed.

The study of complexation equilibria of metal ion with the fragments of the enzyme system involved in the presence of the antibiotic drug is useful in elucidating the mechanism of action of the drug¹. The present communication reports the results of the study of metal-cephalexin-alanine equilibria in solution using Irving-Rossotti method².

Results and Discussion

Conductometric studies of the metal-drug and metal-alanine equilibria in solution utilising the mono-variation method³ indicate formation of two complexes in these systems, with the metal-drug or metal-alanine molar ratios 1 : 1 and 1 : 2, respectively. Addition of third molecule of the ligand does not take place probably due to steric hindrance of the bulky molecules in accordance with the earlier reports with penicillin and cephalosporin group of drugs^{4,5}.

The pH-titration curves in cases of cephalixin and alanine lie before the acid curve, indicating that in acidic solutions each molecule of the ligand is in association with one equivalent of proton. This proton should be attached with the lone-pair of electrons present on the nitrogen of the β -lactam thiozolidine ring in case of cephalixin and on the nitrogen of amino group in case of alanine as indicated in the earlier studies⁴. This corresponds with the two successive steps of deprotonation of the protonated ligands,

Equation (1) corresponds with the ionisation of the carboxyl group of the ligands, while equation (2) denotes deprotonation of the proton attached to the nitrogen atom. The former takes place in the pH range 3.5–5 while the later in pH 6.5–10. Earlier reports^{4–6} also indicate similar steps of de-protonation for the protonated species of penicillin and cephalosporins drugs and alanine.

The titration curves reveal the formation of different M^{II} : drug (cephalexin) binary complexes below pH 6.4. This is clear from the divergence of each of the 1 : 1 binary M^{II} -drug titration curve from that of the corresponding free drug curve, in the pH 5–8, region; beyond this, formation of hydroxy species is indicated. The curves also indicate that the 1 : 1 : 1 mixed ligand complexes are formed at pH values higher than those corresponding to the formation of the binary complexes of the drug, in the step-wise manner, similar to the formation of 1 : 2 binary complexes,

where, ${}^+\text{HL}^-$ = protonated cephalixin ion, and HAH^+ = protonated alanine molecule.

Proton-ligand constants ($\log K_n^{\text{H}}$) and metal-ligand formation constants of 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 binary and 1 : 1 : 1 ternary complexes are recorded in Table 1. With the increase in temperature, the $\log K_n^{\text{H}}$, $\log K_{\text{ML}}^{\text{M}}$, $\log K_{\text{MLA}}^{\text{ML}}$ values decrease, indicating exothermic nature of complexation reactions,

It is interesting to note that the ternary complexes (MLA) are comparatively more stable than the corresponding 1:2 binary complexes of the drug, but they have low stability compared to the corresponding M^{II} -drug binary complexes, i.e. $K_{\text{ML}}^{\text{M}} > K_{\text{MLA}}^{\text{ML}}$. Due to statistical, steric and electrostatic considerations the stability constant for the stepwise formation of 1 : 1 : 1 ternary (MLA) complex is expected to be smaller than the corresponding binary system and the values of $\Delta \log K (= \log K_{\text{MLA}}^{\text{ML}} - \log K_{\text{ML}}^{\text{M}})$ should be negative⁷, as obtained in the present investigation.

Table 1. Stability constants and thermodynamic parameters

$\mu = 0.1 M$ (NaClO₄), Temp. (a) = 25° and (b) 35°

Constant	H	Co	Ni	Cu	Zn
$\log K_n^H$	(a) = 3.50 ^y (b) = 3.25 ^y				
$\log K_2^H$	(a) = 5.60 ^y (b) = 5.60 ^y				
$\log K_{ML}^M$		(a) = 5.92 ^x 5.90 ^y (b) = 5.60 ^x 5.60 ^y	(a) = 5.72 ^x 5.70 ^y (b) = 5.42 ^x 5.40 ^y	(a) = 7.80 ^x 7.80 ^y (b) = 7.20 ^x 7.15 ^y	(a) = 6.12 ^x 6.05 ^y (b) = 5.82 ^x 5.75 ^y
$\log K_{ML_2}^{ML}$		(a) = 4.25 ^x 4.20 ^y (b) = 3.95 ^x 3.86 ^y	(a) = 3.65 ^x 3.57 ^y (b) = 3.52 ^x 3.50 ^y	(a) = 5.60 ^x 5.50 ^y (b) = 5.05 ^x 5.08 ^y	(a) = 5.39 ^x 5.34 ^y (b) = 5.35 ^x 5.29 ^y
$\log K_{MLA}^{ML}$		(a) = 5.53 ^x 5.56 ^y (b) = 5.21 ^x 5.25 ^y	(a) = 4.41 ^x 4.44 ^y (b) = 4.96 ^x 4.95 ^y	(a) = 7.18 ^x 7.21 ^y (b) = 6.52 ^x 6.48 ^y	(a) = 5.61 ^x 5.60 ^y (b) = 5.31 ^x 5.32 ^y
$\Delta \log K$		-0.35 ^b	-0.45 ^b	-0.67 ^b	-0.43 ^b
$\log (K_{MLA}^{ML} - K_{ML}^M)$					
$-\Delta G^\circ$ (kcal mol ⁻¹)		7.45 ^b	7.03 ^b	9.20 ^b	7.55 ^b
$-\Delta H^\circ$ (kcal mol ⁻¹)		13.09 ^b	20.69 ^b	30.40 ^b	11.28 ^b
$-\Delta S^\circ$ (cal K ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹)		18.31 ^b	44.35 ^b	68.83 ^b	12.11 ^b

^xHalf-integral method. ^yLeast-square method.

The less negative values of the stability qualifying factor, ($\Delta \log K$) (Table 1), in general indicate greater stabilisation of ternary complexes⁸, compared to that of the 1 : 2 binary (ML₂) complexes of the drug. The order of stability with reference to metal ions is : Ni^{II} < Co^{II} < Zn^{II} < Cu^{II}.

The negative values of ΔG show that the driving tendency of the complexation reaction is from left to right and the reaction tends to proceed spontaneously.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of A.R. grade. Pure samples of cephalexin (Lupin Pharma) was used.

The standardisation of the metal ions and ligand solutions, and the experimental details were the same as reported earlier⁴.

Stoichiometry of the complexes was ascertained by conductometric titrations. The Calvin-Bjerrum's pH-titration technique as modified by Irving and Rossotti² was applied to determine formation constants. For pH-titrations the following thermostated mixtures were titrated with a carbonate-free 0.1 M NaOH solution : (a) 10 ml 0.04 M HClO₄ +

1 M NaClO₄, (b) Mixture (a) + 5 ml 0.004 M cephalexin, (c) Mixture (a) + 5 ml 0.004 M alanine, (d) Mixture (b) + 10 ml 0.002 M metal, (e) Mixture (c) + 10 ml 0.002 M metal, (f) Mixture (b) + 5 ml 0.004 M alanine, (g) Mixture (f) + 10 ml 0.002 M metal. The ionic strength of the solutions were maintained at 0.1 M by adding required amount of 1.0 M NaClO₄ solution and the total volume of the solution was kept at 50 ml by the adding distilled water.

The values of \bar{n}_A , \bar{n} and pL were calculated by using the Irving-Rossotti equations². Proton-ligand stability constant (K_n^H) was obtained by using the half-integral and the pointwise calculation methods. The values of $\log K_{ML}^M$, $K_{ML_2}^{ML}$ and K_{MLA}^{ML} for the metal complexes were obtained from the formation curves. The refined values were obtained by the least-square method.

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Note

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